

1 **Phosphatase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease: PPEF1.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Up to 50% of patients with HER2+ subtype breast cancer develop metastasis to the central nervous
7 system, most commonly the brain, demanding rapid therapeutic approaches to limit spread of the HER2+
8 primary tumor to distant sites (1-3). We recently described the existence of a group of genes that reside
9 proximal to *ERBB2* (the gene that encodes the human epidermal growth factor *HER2*) at 17q12: their
10 differential expression in HER2+ breast cancer, their up-regulation in HER2+ breast cancer, their
11 differential expression and up-regulation in central nervous system (CNS) metastasis and, based on
12 human survival studies, their function in supporting metastasis to the CNS, indicating that the predilection
13 of HER2+ patients to develop CNS metastasis was a phenomena attributable to the disease and not
14 HER2+-targeted therapies (4). Disease recurrence following disease remission (relapse), resistance to
15 trastuzumab or otherwise inadequate long-term control of disease are challenges that limit effectiveness of
16 existing HER2+-targeted therapies. We utilized whole transcriptome technologies (5, 6) to measure total
17 transcription in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer. We describe here one member
18 of a group of phosphatases up-regulated and differentially expressed in human HER2+ breast cancer,
19 PPEF1, as a catalytically available phosphatase and candidate therapeutic target for the prevention and
20 management of CNS metastasis in HER2+ breast cancer.
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

CRISPR-based reverse genetic screening of human HER2+ organoids or primary tumor cells freshly isolated from patients with HER2+ breast cancer with limited exposure to artificial culture conditions have not yet been described (7, 8). These genetic technologies, though not yet implemented, when done so will likely facilitate discovery of therapeutic vulnerabilities in HER2+ disease with rapidity and ease. Management of major public health problems requires research (bench)-based management in the short run and long run (9). One example of such a major problem is CNS metastasis in HER2+ breast cancer (10-13): this is a type of cancer that affects a human sex with relatively high frequency, a subtype of that cancer that is diagnosed in approximately one quarter of patients diagnosed with that cancer, and a specific complication of that subtype develops in half of affected patients.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with breast cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies to blindly identify disease-specific, subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe one such target identified through rigorous study of the HER2+ tumor transcriptome: a phosphatase target that is up-regulated, catalytically available and subtype-specific: PPEF1.

Results

Figure 1: PPEF1 is differentially expressed in HER2+ breast cancer.

I. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

n=39 primary tumors (breast; human; HER2+)

n=422 primary tumors (breast; human; luminal A, luminal B, basal-like and normal-like)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
206547_s_at	0.04644617	1.9966881	-3.9006	0.11191141	PPEF1	2026/22283	90.9

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in primary tumors of patients with HER2+ breast cancer and in primary tumors of humans with luminal A, luminal B, and basal-like breast cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of protein phosphatase with EF-hand domain 1, encoded by *PPEF1* in HER2+ breast cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of PPEF1 changed more than 90% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,283 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating increased quantity of PPEF1 messenger RNA in HER2+ subtype tumors as compared to other molecular subtypes.

II. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

n=18 primary tumors (breast; human; HER2+)

n=105 primary tumors (breast; human; luminal A, luminal B, basal-like and normal-like)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
8166314	1.76E-02	2.406525	-3.46332	0.48318829	PPEF1	3550/33297	89.3

1 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+
2 breast cancers and in the primary tumors of luminal A, luminal B, basal-like and normal-like subtypes, in a
3 second microarray dataset (6) from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated
4 differential expression of PPEF1 in HER2+ breast cancer in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of PPEF1
5 here changed more than nearly 90% of the human breast tumor transcriptome when considering all
6 transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative
7 fold-change indicating decreased quantity of PPEF1 messenger RNA in HER2+ subtype tumors relative to
8 other molecular subtypes of non-HER2+ origin.

9 Thus, differential and increased expression of PPEF1 defines the transcriptional landscape of the
10 HER2+ breast cancer subtype in humans.

11 **Discussion**

12 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
13 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
14 trastuzumab). Small molecule inhibitors of PPEF1 phosphatase, once evaluated for toxicity and safety,
15 can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with HER2+ metastasis, with the goal of identifying the
16 most effective phosphatase inhibitors for management of HER2+ disease in humans and utilizing these
17 adjunctive phosphatase inhibitors early in disease to prevent rather than treat CNS disease. We recently
18 used primary tumor transcriptome data to identify multiple phosphatases that we deemed candidate
19 therapeutic targets in management of breast cancer, and fortuitously found their decreased expression
20 was specifically linked to superior overall survival in patients with HER2+ breast cancer (14, 15). A
21 multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis,
22 replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase is most likely to be most effective
23 in limiting tumor clone resistance (16).
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Murthy, R.K., Loi, S., Okines, A., Paplomata, E., Hamilton, E., Hurvitz, S.A., Lin, N.U., Borges, V., Abramson, V., Anders, C. and Bedard, P.L., 2020. Tucatinib, trastuzumab, and capecitabine for HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 382(7), pp.597-609.
2. Stavrou, E., Winer, E.P. and Lin, N.U., 2021. How we treat HER2-positive brain metastases. *ESMO open*, 6(5), p.100256.
3. Kay, C., Martínez-Pérez, C., Meehan, J., Gray, M., Webber, V., Dixon, J.M. and Turnbull, A.K., 2021. Current trends in the treatment of HR+/HER2+ breast cancer. *Future Oncology*, 17(13), pp.1665-1681.
4. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
5. GSE158309: Heimes, A.S., Härtner, F., Almstedt, K., Krajnak, S., Lebrecht, A., Battista, M.J., Edlund, K., Brenner, W., Hasenburg, A., Sahin, U. and Gehrmann, M., 2020. Prognostic significance of interferon- γ and its signaling pathway in early breast cancer depends on the molecular subtypes. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(19), p.7178.
6. GSE87049: Romero-Cordoba, S.L., Salido-Guadarrama, I., Rebollar-Vega, R., Bautista-Piña, V., Dominguez-Reyes, C., Tenorio-Torres, A., Villegas-Carlos, F., Fernández López, J.C., Uribe-Figueroa, L., Alfaro-Ruiz, L. and Hidalgo-Miranda, A., 2021. Comprehensive omic characterization of breast cancer in Mexican-Hispanic women. *Nature communications*, 12(1), pp.1-1.
7. Koike-Yusa, H., Li, Y., Tan, E.P., Velasco-Herrera, M.D.C. and Yusa, K., 2014. Genome-wide recessive genetic screening in mammalian cells with a lentiviral CRISPR-guide RNA library. *Nature biotechnology*, 32(3), pp.267-273.
8. Shah, A.N., Davey, C.F., Whitebirch, A.C., Miller, A.C. and Moens, C.B., 2015. Rapid reverse genetic screening using CRISPR in zebrafish. *Nature methods*, 12(6), pp.535-540.
9. Pan, A., Liu, L., Wang, C., Guo, H., Hao, X., Wang, Q., Huang, J., He, N., Yu, H., Lin, X. and Wei, S., 2020. Association of public health interventions with the epidemiology of the COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan, China. *Jama*, 323(19), pp.1915-1923.
10. Lin, N.U. and Winer, E.P., 2007. Brain metastases: the HER2 paradigm. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 13(6), pp.1648-1655.
11. Ponzoni, O., Antonelli, G., Martinelli, G., Baglio, F., Zaniboni, S., Canino, F., Barbolini, M., Molinaro, A., Moscetti, L., Piacentini, F. and Dominici, M., 2024. 208P Clinicopathological factors and treatment management in HER2+ breast cancer patients with central nervous system metastasis. *ESMO Open*.
12. Nader-Marta, G., Martins-Branco, D. and De Azambuja, E., 2022. How we treat patients with metastatic HER2-positive breast cancer. *ESMO open*, 7(1), p.100343.
13. Leyland-Jones, B., 2009. Human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-positive breast cancer and central nervous system metastases. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 27(31), pp.5278-5286.
14. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. The phosphatase PPP4C is differentially expressed in breast cancer and its expression associates with human survival.
15. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. The phosphatase PLPP2 is differentially expressed in breast cancer and its expression associates with human survival.
16. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We utilized GSE158309 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in HER2+ primary tumors from humans with breast cancer, as compared to primary tumors of luminal A, luminal B and basal-like subtypes (non-HER2+ subtypes) (along with GSE87049 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).